

THE ROLE OF MULTIMEDIA IN THE PROCESS OF SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION

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Abstract: This article focuses on the importance of the new equipment that is now widely used in serial translation, the rules, the secrets of rapid writing, and the relevance of the field today. Nowadays, it is extremely important to have modern innovative knowledge and skills in order to become a mature and competent conference interpreter. It is known that the "art of quick writing" is mainly used in consecutive translation, in the process of working with long lectures, as well as in situations where the translator is required to prepare a transcript or a conversation record in a short period of time during negotiations. Some fast typing methods are used to simultaneously translate and record accurate, complete information. This article focuses on such important features of the topic.

Keywords: simultaneous translation, lexical technique, multimedia, innovative technologies, modern technology, international abbreviations, equipment, certificate.

Synchronous translation is a high-level interspecific transfer associated with time limits. The translator needs to complete the source language quickly in a very short time and listen to the source language. Analyzing, understanding, memorizing and converting, observing, organizing, changing and expressing the target language, speaking the target language translation. Interpreters at various international conferences need a "sense of light" and excellent language skills to successfully navigate the hustle and bustle of interrelated and multifaceted tasks. Simultaneous interpretation allows the brain to focus on the lack of energy or the difficulty of distribution.

According to the AIIC (Association of International Conference Interpreters), it is almost impossible to translate 80% of a speaker's 90% to 100% of an interpreter's translation. Many people usually speak very quickly, the speech often takes care of the content of their speech, simultaneous interpretation and even doping around the attention, even the interpreter-interpreter mobilizes all the reserves of knowledge and experience to get out. had to do. With this, the interpreter can deliberately slow down to take care of the speaker, as a result, there are not too many who put too high demands on the quality of practitioners. The threshold for simultaneous interpreting is very high, and the ideal situation is to receive training in formal meetings for translation education,

simultaneous interpretation to build a foundation of good language and skills, and then gain experience through practical translation tasks.

In addition to strong language skills, the mature experience of the meeting should also require a strong desire for knowledge in this field, because for professional needs, translators must have knowledge in many fields at the same time, therefore "simultaneous interpreting" half of the experts in any field, learning a broad knowledge is an essential prerequisite for simultaneous interpreting. Simultaneous interpreting is both an art and a technique. Simultaneous interpretation is carried out together with the statement of the speaker of the original language. Translation should be completed after the first speaker's speech (or at the same time). Therefore, the translator maximizes the translation process and shortens the time interval between the translation and the original language. Simultaneous translation The greater the time difference, the more memory the translator has and the more information is translated. English and Chinese word order means the original meaning, as the translation gives the original meaning when it does not match the original language speaker. Therefore, "sentence is one of the most important features of English and Chinese simultaneous translation".

Simultaneous Translation Equipment

1. Introducing the product to simultaneous translation equipment

Team travel program Shenzhen Rich century electronics company has launched electronic task and mobile simultaneous translation system to achieve intelligent voice to interpret the task. For government officials and VIP customers attending large-scale meetings, the system's equipment, light and modern appearance, cannot use the traditional method to solve the flow of sign language and navigation services, attractions such as museums, theme parks, monuments, attractions.

2. Product specification of simultaneous translation equipment

3. Product application of simultaneous translation equipment

☑ For factory, hospital, school, museum, art gallery, tourist spots, etc., especially for multiple group visits at the same time

☑ Mosque sermon

☑ Concerts

☑ Multimedia education / training

Wireless / Sports

☑ Multiple simultaneous translation

4. Questions of simultaneous translation equipment

(1) Q: How long can we get the shipping and package?

A: As we have a reliable shipping company, we recommend the best and cheapest way to express to different countries. Usually, we keep enough stock and can ship it after we receive the payment. It takes 3-5 business days to arrive.

(2) Q: Do you have certificate?

A: Of course, our product has approved CE, RoHS, FCC.

(3) Q: How many days for sample and mass production?

A: sample delivery time: 1-3 days, mass production time: 7-10 days.

(4) Q: Quality guarantee?

A: We guarantee 100% customer satisfaction. First, quality comes first. We always pay special attention to quality control from beginning to end.

Studies in the field of interpretation and translation have offered various models with which to explore the nature of the interpreting process, whether using simultaneous or consecutive interpreting. Often many people mistakenly assume about translators and interpreters, which make them exchange positions. Not many people can speak in two different foreign languages, especially if more than three can be called multilingual or polyglot. But the problem is that not all foreign language learners have the confidence to become interpreters. In this research, students faced four main difficulties in interpreting, namely a lack of mastery of the source or target language, poor abilities in listening and speaking, insufficient speed adaptability, and inaccuracy. Many people think that interpreters are the same as translators, so many people don't know who interpreter is. The translation is a polysemantic word, which used in different senses, even in the same text stated that as a generic term, referring to both the written and oral transfer of a message from one language to another, or as a specific term designating most often written assignment. Meanwhile, interpreting is the process of translating of spoken language from source language into target language. It is stated that interpreting is a complex task where the interpreter is routinely involved in comprehending, bringing, and producing style at the same time.

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